

COMMUNICATION OUTPUTS

1. MEDIA COVERAGE

1.1 Media Coverage Following The Initial Project Announcement

Title: EU Grants Full Support to Climate Resilience Project for Dairy Farms in Aydin

Description:

This press release reports that the Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydin (CBAA) received full EU funding for its project "Enhancing Climate Resilience in Dairy Farms" under the CLIMAAX framework. Selected among 119 proposals from 36 countries, the project was awarded a €146,000 grant and became one of four projects representing Türkiye. The coverage highlights the project's objective to strengthen the resilience of dairy farming systems in Aydin against climate change impacts, including extreme weather events, through the development of climate adaptation strategies.

Sources:

- İhlas News Agency (İHA)
- Manşet Aydin
- Aydin Hızlı Haber

Date: 30.10.2024

Language: Turkish

Links:

<https://www.ihacom.tr/Aydin-haberleri/adsyb-ineklerin-kuresel-iklim-krizinin-olumsuz-etkilerini-azaltmak-icin-proje-hazirladi-136494438>

<https://www.mansetAydin.com/haber/22221246/abden-tam-destek>

<https://Aydinhizlihaber.com/Aydin-avrupa-birliginden-hibe-alan-projeler-arasinda-yer-aldi-7149>

Dissemination note:

This press release was disseminated through three different local and regional media outlets, enhancing public awareness of the CLIMAAX – CliResDairy project and its objectives.

1.1.2 Project News Item 2

Title: ADSYB Climate Resilience Project Followed with Interest at Barcelona Workshop

Description:

This media coverage reports on the participation of the Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydin (CBAA) in an international workshop held in Barcelona within the scope of the CLIMAAX project. The articles highlight that the CliResDairy project, aimed at enhancing climate resilience in dairy farming, attracted significant attention during the workshop, where project objectives, methodologies, and preliminary outcomes were shared with international stakeholders. The coverage emphasizes the project's contribution to knowledge exchange and international visibility within the CLIMAAX framework.

Sources:

- Aydin Havadisleri
- Önder Haber
- İhlas News Agency (İHA)
- Manşet Aydın

Date: 17.06.2025

Language: Turkish

Links:

- <https://Aydinhavadisleri.com/Aydin-ili-damizlik-sigir-yetistiricileri-birliginin-projesi-barselonada-ilgiyle-takip-edildi/>
- <https://www.onderhaber.com.tr/Aydin-ili-damizlik-sigir-yetistiricileri-birliginin-projesi-barselonada-ilgiyle-takip-edildi>
- <https://www.ihacom.tr/Aydin-haberleri/aydin-ili-damizlik-sigir-yetistiricileri-birliginin-projesi-barselonada-ilgiyle-takip-edildi-254699098>
- <https://www.mansetAydin.com/haber/25265510/Aydinin-projesi-barselonada>

Dissemination note:

This media coverage resulted from the dissemination of project-related activities at an international CLIMAAX workshop and was published across multiple local and regional media outlets, strengthening the project's international visibility and stakeholder awareness.

1.1.3 Project News Item 3

Title: Climate Resilience in Dairy Farming Discussed at CliResDairy Stakeholder Workshop in Aydın

Description:

This media coverage reports on the CliResDairy Project Stakeholder Workshop held in Aydın, focusing on strengthening climate resilience in dairy farming. The articles highlight discussions among dairy producers, public institutions, agricultural organisations, and academic experts on key climate risks affecting the sector, including heat stress, drought, and flooding. The

workshop addressed both challenges and adaptation approaches for dairy farms and is presented as a core participatory activity of the CLIMAAX project, supporting stakeholder engagement and regional knowledge exchange.

Sources:

- İhlas News Agency (İHA)
- SonDakika.com
- Manşet Aydın
- Ege Alternatif
- Haber Ekspres
- Aydın Denge

Date: 24.12.2025

Language: Turkish

Links:

- <https://www.ihacom.tr/aydin-haberleri/aydinda-sut-ciftlikleri-icin-iklim-dayanikligi-masaya-yatirildi-351686314>
- <https://www.sondakika.com/amp/haber-iklim-degisikligi-ve-sutculuk-aydin-da-proje-calis-19387468/>
- <https://www.mansetaydin.com/haber/27106746/aydinda-sut-calistayi>
- https://www.egealternatif.com/foto/aydin-daki-sut-ciftlikleri-iklim-degisikligine-karsi-direnc-gelistiriyor_53284/
- <https://www.haberekspres.com.tr/aydinda-sut-sigirciligi-icin-iklim-direnci-masaya-yatirildi>
- <https://www.aydindenge.com.tr/aydin/24/12/2025/aydinda-sut-ciftlikleri-icin-iklim-dayanikligi-masaya-yatirildi>

Dissemination note:

This media coverage resulted from the dissemination of the CliResDairy regional stakeholder workshop and was published across multiple local and regional media outlets, contributing to increased awareness of climate resilience challenges and adaptation strategies for dairy farming within the CLIMAAX framework.

2. CBAA WEBSITE ANNOUNCEMENTS

2.1 Website Announcement 1

Title: CliResDairy Project Stakeholder Workshop Successfully Held

Description:

This website announcement reports on the successful organisation of the CliResDairy Project Stakeholder Workshop by the Cattle Breeder's Association of Aydın (CBAA). The announcement highlights the objectives of the workshop, stakeholder participation, and key discussion themes related to climate risks and resilience in dairy farming. The event is presented

as an important milestone within the CLIMAAX project, supporting regional stakeholder engagement and knowledge exchange.

Source: Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydin (CBAA)– Official Website

Language: Turkish

Link: <https://www.adsyb.org.tr/haber/cliresdairy-projesi-calistayimizi-gerceklestirdik/>

Dissemination note:

This website announcement contributed to informing stakeholders and the wider public about the implementation of a key participatory activity within the CLIMAAX – CliResDairy project.

2.2 Website Announcement 2

Title: European Regions Move Forward to Strengthen Climate Resilience

Description:

This website announcement highlights international cooperation activities under the CLIMAAX framework, reporting on the engagement of 33 European regions working towards enhancing climate resilience. The announcement emphasizes the role of regional collaboration, knowledge sharing, and coordinated action in addressing climate risks, while positioning the CliResDairy project within a broader European climate resilience context.

Source: Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydin (CBAA)– Official Website

Language: Turkish

Link: <https://www.adsyb.org.tr/haber/33-avrupa-bolgesi-iklim-dayanikligini-artirmayolunda-hareket-ediyor/>

Dissemination note:

This website announcement supported the dissemination of CLIMAAX-related information and reinforced the visibility of the CliResDairy project within a wider European network of climate resilience initiatives.

3. SOCIAL MEDIA DISSEMINATION

Description:

Project announcements, updates, and key outputs have also been disseminated through the official Facebook and LinkedIn accounts of the Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydin (CBAA), contributing to the visibility of the CLIMAAX – CliResDairy project among sector stakeholders.